

(Jewels of meanings and fulfillment of wishes) جواهر المعاني و بلوغ الأمان

also known as "Jawahir al-Ma'ani wa Bulug al-Amani"

By Bilyaminu Muhammad, Umaru Musa 'Yar-Adua University Katsina, Nigeria

Entry tags: Religious Group, Islamic Law, Arabic, Text, Sufism, Language, Islamic Traditions

The text was composed to describe the biographical style of the founder of the Tijjaniyyah Sufi Order, Shiekh Ahmad al-Tijjani, who lived an exemplary trend that all the order's followers should emulate on a journey to attain a high level of spiritual sanctity. The author starts with the first seven chapters of the founder's biography, followed by the daily services for every follower, such as repentance, praises to the Prophet Muhammad (SAW), and the word of testimony to Allah. Other sections discussed are the ethics and moral principles of the Sufi order, which every follower shall live by. The Order is widely accepted in most of the African Muslim world which has a lot of followers in some territories of the Sokoto Caliphate who have devoted themselves to its principal duties throughout their lives.

Date Range: 1804 CE - 1903 CE

Region: Sokoto

Region tags: Africa, Western Africa, Benin, Burkina Faso, Niger, Togo, Nigeria, Chad, Cameroon

Sokoto around 1870, during the reign of Ahmadu Rufai. Adapted from AbdurRahman AbdulMoneim [https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_\(cropped\).png](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_(cropped).png)

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: علي حرازم. جواهر المعاني و بلوغ الأمان في فيض سيدي أبي العباس التجاني رضيا لله عنه. دار الفك. بيوت لبنان. 2012

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

— Source 1 URL: https://www.noor-book.com/book/internal_download/707c317d96abd8e01ad8dfbd874f3a6d1ecf9aa5/3/ce37a0c8e026748fa8ec8f9a3eb

— Source 1 Description: Noor Book

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.ktobati-pdf.com/book/download/a1cdf1c5-6324-48df-90be-6db7694d6084>

– Source 1 Description: Ktobati

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Inked

–with Ink

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Specify type of paper

–Specify: White

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Tomb

— No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Cemetery

— No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Temple

— No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Shrine

— No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Altar

— No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Devotional marker

— No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Cenotaph

— No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ **Church**
– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ **Mosque**
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ **Synagogue**
– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ **Triumphal Arch**
– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ **Monument**
– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ **Mass Gathering Point**
– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ **Cave(s)**
– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ **Hilltops**
– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ **Other natural sanctuaries**
– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ **Boundary markers or lines**
– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ **Domestic contexts**
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ **Library/archive**
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ **Specify**
– Specify: **Bookshop**

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Present full-time?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Present part-time?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious specialists?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

–Total audience: 5000000

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (estimated population, numerical)

–Number: 3000000

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

–smallest audience: 1000000

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

–largest audience: 5000000

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

–Specify: Birthrate and Deathrate.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (% of sample region population, numerical)

–Number: 10000000

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

–smallest audience: 2000000

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

–largest audience: 8000000

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size
– Specify: Birthrate and Deathrate.

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ Nature of audience

[select all that apply]

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ Can scholarly and emic notions of the audience differ?

– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Are rewards for missionary work promised by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Are rewards for missionary work promised by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific time?
– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific place?
– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ Is normative proselytizing directed toward a specific audience?
– Yes

Notes: The proselytization is aimed at all non-Tijjaniya followers in the region.

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?
– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?
– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Is it orally recited?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Is it read?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

– Specify: The text described the ritual practices of the Tijjaniya movement.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Number of participants: 100

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Number of participants: 2

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– Specify: Three times daily.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

Notes: Some versions accompany commentaries.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The text remodels the spirituality of humans.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual list

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

|

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ In cemetery?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Other formal burial type?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

– Specify: Bathing, shrouding and funeral prayer.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: Creation of all beings.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Can reward

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Can punish

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

– Specify: Creation.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ A supreme high-god is present

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Status of Readership:

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Status of Readership:

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Status of Readership:

↳ Possesses Hunger?

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Status of Readership:

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

– Specify: Descend rainfall.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ In dreams

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ In trance possession

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Through divination practices

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Only through religious specialists

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

Notes: Inspiration.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ In waking, everyday life

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ In dreams

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ In trance possession

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Through divination practices

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Communicate through other means

– Specify: Mysterious

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature
– Specify: Mysterious movement.

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

Are other categories of beings present?

– Mysterious?

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Incest

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Other sexual practices

– Yes

Notes: Sodomy and lesbianism are prohibited.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Food

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Sacred space(s)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Sacred object(s)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Adultery

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Incest

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Other sexual practices

– Yes

Notes: Sodomy and lesbianism are prohibited.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ **Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders**
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ **Supernatural beings care about gossiping**
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ **Supernatural beings care about property crimes**
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ **Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance**
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ **Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals**
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ **Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists**
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ **Supernatural beings care about economic fairness**
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ **Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene**
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about other
– Specify: Animals.

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm?
– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ Other form of punishment
– Specify: Extreme burning in the hellfire.

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

Notes: They punish according to the directives of the High God.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Done randomly

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Other

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Punishments in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

|

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Other form of punishment

– Specify: Extreme burning in the hellfire.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

|

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Done randomly

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Consists of eternal happiness?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Other?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

|

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

|

↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Consists of eternal happiness?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– No

Notes: The reward is only recorded in this life.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ **At specified time in future**
– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ **At unspecified time in near future**
– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ **At unspecified time in distant future**
– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ **At some other time [specify]**
– Yes

Notes: The actual time of the eschaton is only known to God.

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ **Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end**
– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ **Divine judgment event**
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ **Restoration of the world**
– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ **Start of a new temporal cycle**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Establishment of new political system

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Establishment of new religious system

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Other form of eschatology?

– Specify: Paradise.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Courage (in battle)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ **Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity**

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ **Respectfulness/courtesy**

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ **Familial obedience/filial piety**

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ **Fidelity/loyalty**

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ **Cooperation**

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ **Independence/creativity/freedom**

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ **Moderation/frugality**

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ **Forbearance/fortitude/patience**

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Strength (physical)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Power/status/nobility

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Optimism/hope

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

- ↳ **Gratitude/thankfulness**
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Status of Readership:

- ↳ **Reverence/awe/wonder**
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Status of Readership:

- ↳ **Faith/belief/trust/devotion**
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Status of Readership:

- ↳ **Wisdom/understanding**
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Status of Readership:

- ↳ **Discernment/intelligence**
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Status of Readership:

- ↳ **Beauty/attractiveness**
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Status of Readership:

- ↳ **Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness**
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Status of Readership:

- ↳ **Other important virtues**
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Status of Readership:

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Does the text require castration?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Does the text require physical risk taking?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Hours: 12

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– Number of participants: 100

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Hours: 24

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Are there orthopraxy checks?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Other forms of welfare?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy permanently?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy temporarily/seasonally?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Does the text dictate how the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Does the text dictate how individuals interact with other institutional bureaucracies?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Does the text regulate the primary supporting income of the place?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out land?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out tools?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Does the text advocate for public food storage?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Does the text provide guidance for food distribution?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Does the text regulate places for civic functions?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Does the text regulate places for the practice of justice?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Does the text advocate or specify controls for water management (irrigation, flood control)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Does the text specify restrictions on common transportation?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Other form of regulation of public works?

– Specify: The text regulates the spiritual appearance of people.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Bibliography

General References

Reference: (Jewels of meanings and fulfillment of wishes) جواهر المعاني و بلوغ الأمانی, Johnston, Hugh A. S.. The Fulani Empire of Sokoto. London: Oxford University Press, 1967. <https://www.worldcat.org/title/5769770>.

Reference: (Jewels of meanings and fulfillment of wishes) جواهر المعاني و بلوغ الأمانی, Last, Murray. The Sokoto Caliphate. New York: Humanities Press, 1967. <https://www.worldcat.org/title/49303>.

Reference: (Jewels of meanings and fulfillment of wishes) جواهر المعاني و بلوغ الأمانی, حرازم, علي. جواهر المعاني و بلوغ الأمانی في فيض سيدي أبي العباس التجاني رضيلله عنه. بيوت لبنان: دار الفكر, 2012.